

Phytogeographical Distribution of *Adhatoda Vasica L.* in NCR Delhi Region

Paper Id : 18022 Submission Date : 16/08/2023 Acceptance Date : 22/08/2023 Publication Date : 25/08/2023

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8383089

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/researchtimes.php#8>

Avinash Kumar
Research Scholar
Botany
MONAD University
,U.P., India,

Avinash Sharma
Assistant Professor Botany
MONAD University
U.P., India

Amar Singh Kashyap
Assistant Professor
Botany
MM (P.G.) College Modinagar
U.P., India

Abstract

Vasaka is a Medicinal plant , mainly used as a crude drug for different ailments. The plant is distributed in all over India and many other countries of temperate region. The present study is carried on *Adhatoda vasica L.* distribution in Delhi NCR region. The region has a lot of consumption of crude drugs along with its historical heritage, geographical area and cultural diversity. It has modern civilization. This region is also known as the planet of Crude Drugs due to rich markets of wild herbal plants. Since historical times *vasica* is also well known as an indigenous herb. The whole plant is beneficial for health, mainly in the treatment of bronchitis using its leaf extracts. Its root and bark decoction is used in the quantity of 10 to 15 grams 3 times a day for 3 days in the treatment of removal of intestinal parasites in rural areas. The juice of *vasica* leaves liquefies thick sputum. Its dry leaves smoking gives relief in asthma. According to Ayurveda, a gulkand made from *vasica* flowers is used in the treatment of tuberculosis. The use of hot decoction of its leaves is useful in the treatment of itching and other skin diseases. Modern medicine has discovered the active constituents are alkaloids in which *vasicin*, *oxyvasicin* and *vasicinone*. In which *vasicin* is an active ingredient to expel sputum in the body. The herb is found in scattered form in the NCR region & now shrinking its production due to over development.

Keywords Adhatoda Vasica, NCR Region, Crude Drug, Herbal Plant.

Introduction

The culture of NCR region is average modern but the people rely on traditional culture also. The medical facilities are very advanced in the region even metro cities people preferred to allopathic medicine for quick treatment but the rural areas people having the attraction with traditional and naturopathy system. The NCR region having dense industrial area and population. It has a lot of number of herbal medicines pharma companies where *Adhatoda vasica* having in constant demand. There are many valuable medicinal plants which are dominated in the region which are supplied regularly in the herbal manufacturing units. A few herbal plants are grown in the agriculture fields by farmers but many more medicinal plants are collected from the wild condition. Most of the herbal plants are in higher demands like *Withania somnifera*, *Adhatoda vasica*, *Boehreria diffusa*, *Achyranthus aspera*, *Xanthium sp.*, *Datura sp.*, etc. We should have recommended the farmers to grow the medicinal plants in agriculture fields to fulfill the constant demand. It will help for sustainable development & conservation. (Sharma 2007,2019) In the present study we found the distribution pattern of *Adhatoda vasica* is locally known as *safed bansa* which is used by local people in cough syrup (*cadha* preparation) in T.B. bronchitis in Jaundice and in immunity development. Sometimes it is also feed to cattle during the birth of calf and lactation period. *Vasica* is used in different ailments of human diseases like eg. T.B., asthma, tuberculosis, Bronchial and other respiratory disease. It is an important component of cough syrup and other herbal medicine *Adhatoda vasica* is belong to family *Acanthaceae* of Angiosperms (dicot) . *Adhatoda vasica* has a great variation in plant height, petiole Length, leaf area, colour, thickness and other macro and micro morphological characters. The plant is also found in the wild area of Delhi NCR

region. NCR region having river ecosystem Sandy plane ecosystem and fertile soil. It has a variety of climates semi- arid and arid conditions. It has moderate rains. Phytogeographical diversity of natural vegetation is affected by Biotic and edaphic condition. Here in the present study, we are concentrated on the distribution of *Adhatoda vasica* in the NCR region.

- Aim of study**
1. To find out the distribution pattern of the studied plant and their demographic presentation from special distribution.
 2. To prepare layout planning map for ongoing plantation program for Applied plant species under study area.
 3. To conserve the plant species for contact, supply the herbal / Crude drug.

Review of Literature

The phytogeographical distribution work was also done by different workers . Medicinal plants & other plants geographical distribution were also done by pharmacognosics . Some scientist did the work on soil, vegetation & distribution pattern (Money 1965 & Sharma 2007) Polunin 1967. Walts, 1971. Rathore (1992) used the remote sensing technique for distribution pattern of plants. Shankar & Kumar (1988) did the work on the ecology of Indian desert area. Kashyap (2002) did the work on medicinal plant & their pharmacognostical studies with germination & distribution patterns. As part of the research work, the flora of the area was also studied by many botanists and their information about its crude drug quality were also given as Linneaus S.C. (1753) in Species his book Plantarum. Koppen (1900) did the work on the classification of the plants. Hooker (1906) did the worked on "A Sketch of the flora of British India". Washington and Raunkiaer (1934) published the book on The Life-forms of the plant and statistical plant geography. Polunin, (1967) Introduced about Plant Geography and some related Science. Watts (1971) Principles of Biogeography. Mani, (1974) did the work on ecology and biogeography of India. Krebs (1978) did the work on Ecology - The experimental analysis of distribution and abundance.

Bachketi (1984) did the work on social forestry in India with the problems and prospects. Bhandari (1990) mentioned the flora of Indian Desert. Dhuley (1999) worked on herbal flora and published on Indian Herbal Pharmacopoeia. Sharma (2007) wrote a book on medicinal plants Geography which was very useful to confirm through literature. Kashyap (2002) did the work on certain medicinal plants habitats and other aspects. Sharma (2019) and Kukreti et al (2023) did the work on Phytogeographical distribution of medicinal plants and vegetation.

Main Text

The proposed study research area is NCR Region has the geographical extension included NCT Delhi, Gautam Buddha Nagar, Ghaziabad, Baghpat, Meerut, Bulandshahar and Some region of Haryana the study area has been included NCT Delhi, Ghaziabad, Gautam Buddha Nagar, Meerut and Baghpat from North- latitude 28°44'42"N and East longitude 77°05'35"E from the area under study is dominated by highly developed region as well as agricultural region. It is highly dense populated area .Delhi NCR region comprises along with Haryana (Gurugram, Rohtak, Faridabad, Karnal, Panipat, Jhajjar, Ambala, Panchkula, Jind, Kurukshetra, Hisar, Sirsa, Kaithal, Sonapat, Palwal, Fatehabad, Yamunanagar, Nuh, Rewari, Bhiwani, Mahendragarh, Charkhi Dadri) UP (Gautam Budh Nagar, Ghaziabad, Hapur, Baghpat) (Map) -

Methodology The present study has been concentrated on extensive field work. The important data of *Adhatoda vasica* L. has been collected from authentic resources. The Survey of India, topo sheet and bioclimatic Map has been used. The map has been taken for entire NCR Delhi region. This data has been collected in addition to reports, maps, research papers books, monographs soil survey data published and unpublished materials from various agencies.

Remote sensing and physical factors like climate, soil types and water quality also helpful to examine the distribution pattern. Biological factors such as flora and fauna, Social factors included population, mobility, economic activities, etc .These were studied after examining the data related to usage and other data (some productivity indicators) have been used in the survey site. The spot to spot survey was completed. The community study of the studied plant was used by Raunkier's method to find out the distribution pattern. Somewhere *Adatoda vasica* was found in dotted form. It is common in some regions some times it was seen in abundant form indifferent areas. The species quality of the *Adhatoda vasica* plant also known by local community . The natural, environmental and climatic conditions for *Adhatoda vassaca* were also studied Phyto-climatic data. A carto - graphic interpretation of the species of *Adhatoda vasica* L. from the point of view of phylogeographic studies were also completed at two levels. ie. at the macro as well as micro level. It could be helpful to complete the phytogeographic observation.

Sampling

The spot to spot survey was completed and calculated by Raunkier's method to find out the distribution pattern. Somewhere *Adatoda vasica* was found in dotted form. It was common in some regions some times it was seen in abundant form in different areas.

Tools Used

Quadrante method, Photography

Result and Discussion

NCR Delhi, has the *vasaca* plant on the waste lands near by roads, rivers and untouched vegetational sites. Phytogeographical distribution pattern of studied plant. It will be helpful in the conservation, analysis and distinctive quality of *Adhatoda vasica* L. in herbaceous species found in different areas of the studied area which covers Ghaziabad, Meerut, Baghpat, Delhi, Haryana and some parts of Rajasthan and many other parts of India.

The studied herbaceous plant *Adhatoda vasica* L. found in the area of Delhi NCR was found deficient in various factors. Also in the successful aspect one can see the results of the efforts made by the Forest Department increasing land under green coverage through tree plantation programs and awareness campaigns. but it has been found *Adhatoda vasica* L. not grown or planted anywhere by forest department & people.

Natural vegetation *Adhatoda vasica* L. is being eroded from Delhi NCR region through irregular rainfall, heavy industrialization, wind erosion, water erosion, high temperature, storm and soil erosion. All these activities have been caused threatend the *Adhatoda vasica* L.